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ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE
ARCHAEOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE
FOR
SAMVAT 1982, YEAR 1925-26.

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Gwalior

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT

OF THE

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY,

GWALIOR STATE,

FOR THE

Year ending 30th June 1926, Samvat 1982.

PART I.

OFFICE NOTES.

Charge.

1. During the year of report the undersigned held charge of the Department except for a month between the 18th of December 1925 and the 17th of January 1926, while he was on privilege leave. During the period of leave the charge of the current duties of the post remained with R. S. Saksena, the Archæological Overseer.

Leave.

2. The Superintendent availed himself of one month's privilege leave from the 18th of December 1925 to the 17th of January 1926.

3. Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows:—

(a) Archæological Overseer: Privilege leave of 7 days from the 1st October to the 7th October 1925.

(b) Photographer-Draughtsman: Privilege leave of 29 days from the 1st July to the 8th July 1925 and from the 29th May to the 18th June 1926, sick leave on medical certificate for one month and eight days from the 9th July to the 16th August 1925 and leave without pay for 12 days from the 19th to the 30th June 1926.

(c) General Assistant: Privilege leave of 39 days from the 11th to the 27th July 1925 and from the 19th December 1925 to the 9th January 1926.

(d) Officer Accounts: Privilege leave of 10 days from the 2nd to the 11th September 1925.

(e) Officer Correspondence: Privilege leave of 26 days from the 18th to the 27th August 1925 and from the 27th January 1926 to the 11th February 1926.

(f) Record-keeper: Privilege leave of 47 days in the several months of the year.

New Post.

4. A new post of the Record-keeper which was sanctioned in the last year's budget was filled up during the year of report. B. B. Chauhan, a Maratha young man who had already put in a year's service in the *Khasgi Karkhana*, being appointed to it.

Promotions.

5. On the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation an increment of Rs. 5 per month was made in the salary of the Officer Accounts and of the Officer Correspondence, as a result of the general order promoting such officers all over the State.

Cash Reward.

6. A Cash Reward of Rupees one hundred (Rs. 100) was conferred on R. S. Khandalkar, Officer Correspondence, on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.

General.

7. All the Office Staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Circulars and Orders.

8. Circular No. 1/1982, Home Department (Section Archaeology), was issued in the *Gwalior Government Gazette* of August 8, 1925. It warns the public against injuring or disfiguring Ancient Monuments in the State or removing any carvings or inscriptions from the ruins of or lying loose on sites of such monuments. Further it advises officers of other Departments in the State to send information to the Archaeological Department whenever they come across cases of violation of the aforesaid order.

III. Work at Headquarters.

9. In addition to the ordinary office routine the following work was done during the Headquarter season :—

- (a) An Annual Administration Report for Saurvat 1981 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) A resumé of the conservation and exploration work accomplished by the Department in the year 1924-25 was contributed to the *All-India Archaeological Survey Report*.
- (c) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were arranged and labelled.
- (d) A circular letter was printed and circulated among the *Jagirdars* and *Thikanedars* in the State inviting them to take interest in, and to co-operate with the work of the Department.
- (e) A similar letter was printed and circulated among the *Zamindars* of the several villages in which ancient monuments are situated.
- (f) A short report of the work of the Department for the last ten years was prepared and printed for free distribution.
- (g) Tourists' agencies such as Messrs. Thos. Cook and Son and the American Express Company were moved for including Gwalior and other places of interest in the State in the programmes of foreign tourists which they arrange.
- (h) Arrangement was made with the G. I. P. Railway for exhibiting photographs of our Archaeological Monuments in the higher class carriages and at stations in the vicinity of which monuments are situated.

- (i) Albums of photographs of interesting monuments were prepared and presented to Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians at the time of Their Majesties' visit to Gwalior and to His Highness the Maharaja Sahib Scindia on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.
- (j) A magic lantern show was given to the boys of the Sardars' School at the Gwalior Fort and another to the Jagirdars assembled at Gwalior on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.

IV. Tours.

10. During the year of report I spent 77 days in camp while my Assistant who officiated for me during my leave toured for 16 days.

11. The tours were undertaken for directing and measuring the conservation works in progress, for annual inspections of monuments already conserved and for exploration of fresh monuments. Thus all the conserved monuments at Gwalior, Narwar, Surwaya, Ranod, Chanderi, Badoh, Udaypur, Bbilsa, Udaygiri, Ujjain, Mandasor and Bagh were inspected in the year of report. We visited Udaypur four times, Mandasor thrice, Narwar, Padhavli and Bagh twice each, and Suhania once, for the supervision and measurements of conservation works going on there. Devadungri in the Ujjain District, Indhar in the Narwar District, and Mahuwan, Deokani and Mamon in the Esagarh District were visited for exploration purposes.

12. I accompanied Prof. Dr. J. Ph. Vogel of the Leiden University (Holland) during his visits to Bagh and Udaygiri caves as State guest.

13. Moreover with the sanction of the Home Member I visited the ruins of the ancient city Vijayanagar (modern Hampi) in the Ballery District of the Madras Presidency and the wonderful rock-cut caves at Ellora, the Fort of Daulatabad and the monuments at Aurangabad in the Hyderabad State. A visit to these important monuments added considerably to my knowledge of Ancient Indian Architecture. I was also benefited by what I saw of the measures of conservation and upkeep carried out at these places by the local Archaeological Departments.

14. A detailed tour diary is given in Appendix No. A.

V. Conservation.

15. Conservation works were carried out at Bagh, Mandasor, Sondni, Udaypur, Narwar, Padhavli and Suhania at a total cost of Rs. 19,254-6-6 including part of the special grant for Narwar Fort.

16. The statement of monuments conserved in the year of report is set forth in Appendix No. B.

17. **Bagh.**—At Bagh the facade of cave No. 2 was freed from the crust of mud and cow-dung with which it was disfigured in modern times by *sadhus*, *bairagis* and others. The front wall has suffered a number of gaps and fissures especially near the doors and windows, by the decaying of the rock. The northern half of the facade was repaired in the year of report. The decaying edges of the rock were carefully cut out and the gaps filled up

by inserting masonry of dressed stone in lime. Towards the northern end large patches of both the inner and outer faces of the wall have had to be thus renewed. The doorway of the cell at the northern end of the verandah had badly decayed. It was also restored in masonry.

18. A few cells in cave No. 2 are filled up almost to the ceiling with bats' dung. They have defied clearance so far as the workmen find it impossible to work continuously for any considerable length of time in an atmosphere surcharged with the filthy dust. A beginning was made this year to clear up the cells and the work will be accomplished gradually in a few years.

19. With a view to develop the work of repairs the collection of building stone was commenced in the year of report and is progressing slowly owing to the want of good building stone in the locality and the absence of easy means of communication between the quarries and the caves.

20. **Mandasor.**—The excellently carved and imposingly large sculpture of Siva (Gupta period) which had been excavated in a ravine at the south-east corner of the Mandasor Fort three years ago, was lifted out of its unseemly abode and planted up decently on a secure foundation in front of the new building of Subat (Collector's Office) in the same fort. A masonry buttress has been set up behind the sculpture to hold it in position and it is further protected by means of a rectangular fence consisting of a course of iron chains carried on stone posts.

21. The excavations indicated that the sculpture, as it was found, was not *in situ* but had been re-erected there some time during or after the mediæval period. Further, as it stood deep in a ravine which carried away the rain water from the major portion of the fort area and got silted up year after year, it would have been very difficult to maintain the sculpture in a clean and tidy condition on that spot. Moreover there was no point in preserving it in that obscure and dirty place. It was therefore shifted to its present site where it occupies a conspicuous position in clean and spacious surroundings so as to attract the attention of visitors.

22. Another piece of sculpture also of the Gupta period which has been brought to the same premises and for similar reasons, is a *Torana* pillar locally known as *Sravan-ki-Kawad*. It originally stood in the narrow, dirty compound of a modern temple in the village Khilchipura about 2 miles to the South of the Mandasor Fort. It is one of the two pillars of a *Torana* or gateway belonging probably to a Saiva temple of the Gupta period. The excavations carried out on the site showed traces of a brick structure probably a part of the original temple. But there were difficulties in preserving the pillar on its original site. Its original ground level was about 6 feet below the present ground level. It was therefore necessary to make a sink 10 feet $\times$ 10 feet $\times$ 6 feet in order to make the whole pillar visible and accessible to visitors. To make such a pit with retaining walls of masonry on all sides and also to provide a long *pucca* drain to carry away rain water would have been an unnecessarily expensive task. Moreover the pillar stood in an out-of-the-way obscure place. So it was preferred to shift it to the compound of the Subat building in the Mandasor Fort, so as to be in a safe and conspicuous place, and easily accessible.

23. There it has been erected on a strong foundation and fenced round with iron chains carried on stone posts. The original site of the pillar will be marked with an inscribed tablet.

24. **Sondni.**—The heaviest and most arduous work of conservation carried out in the year was that relating to the huge monoliths of Yasodharman lying in a field at Sondni about $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the south-east of Mandasor Fort. The columns are inscribed in Gupta characters and record the eulogy of king Yasodharman who flourished about the middle of the 6th century A. C. There are two such columns, exact duplicates of each other, with shafts about 40 feet in length and $3\frac{1}{2}$ feet in section surmounted each by two capitals besides a double faced figure as the crest. For a detailed description of the columns see Dr. Fleet's *Gupta Inscriptions*, pp. 142-46. The columns were lying prostrate in a broken and uncared for condition half buried in earth. The shaft of one of these is broken into two pieces, both the pieces being intact. The shaft of the other column is split into a number of pieces some of which are missing. All the four capitals were lying scattered in a neighbouring field. A double faced head of one of the crowning figures was recovered in the excavations. In order to save these valuable relics from further damage and oblivion all these heavy pieces were dug up, lifted, properly arranged, and exhibited on a strong masonry platform 60 feet $\times$ 15 feet specially constructed for the purpose on the site. As some of the pieces weighed as much as 250 maunds it was no easy task to move them to their new position.

25. Two big sculptures of *Dvarapalas* which are contemporary with and very probably belonged to this monument in some way or other were lying half buried in the same field. These were picked up and set up to flank the approach to the platform.

26. A rectangular area of 155 feet $\times$ 115 feet in the centre of which the platform is located has been freed from jungle, levelled, tidied up and fenced round with three lines of wire carried on stone posts, entrance being provided through a revolving gate. As the locality is rather barren it is proposed to plant trees at the corners of the compound and provide a few stone seats for visitors.

27. A stone inscription giving a brief account of the pillars both in Hindi and English has been set up close by, for the information of visitors. The original foundations of the pillars which were exposed during the excavations carried out here three years ago, have been marked by inscribed stone slabs. Thus every care has been taken to protect the monument from further damage, to mark its original site, and to present it in an attractive and intelligible form.

28. **Udaypur.**—The *kachcha* houses trespassing into the original compound of the Udayesvar temple were acquired by Government towards the end of the last year. As these houses blocked up and disfigured the view of the great temple, they were dismantled and their debris removed to a safe distance. The original compound has thus been freed from all unnecessary and ugly encumbrances. After the removal of these houses it was found that in the compound wall the original portion survives only here and there and the varied patches of restorations made in later times have themselves become dilapidated or damaged in several places. To dismantle the whole wall and

rebuild it in a uniform pattern of masonry though desirable would entail enormous expenses. It is therefore proposed to repair only the badly bulging or dilapidated portions, to reduce the wall to a uniform height by levelling down taller and raising up shorter portions and making the top water-tight.

29. The original entrance to the enclosure flanked by an elaborately carved figure of *Dearapala* on either side has been exposed in the East enclosure wall. This passage will be cleaned up and properly maintained.

30. **Narwar.**—In continuation of the repairs to ancient monuments on the Fort carried out last year, the small Roman Catholic Church erected by a company of European gunners employed by the Rajas of Narwar in the middle of the 18th century and referred to by General Cunningham (*C. A. S. R.*, Vol. II, pp. 322-23) was attended to in the year of report. The enclosure wall of the compound in which the chapel stands was repaired and the enclosed area was freed from jungle and tidied up.

31. Two tombs of Armenian missionaries, one inside and the other outside the town of Narwar, were liberated from jungle and rubbish with which they had been covered. Their surroundings were further tidied up.

32. Stone inscriptions in Hindi and English giving the names and short descriptions (wherever necessary) were put upon or near most of the important monuments conserved.

33. **Padhavli.**—In the small ruined fort (*gadhi*) at Padhavli about 20 miles to the north of Gwalior are the remnants of a 10th century Siva Temple. This temple stood on an extensive platform in the midst of a set of attendant shrines. Three or four centuries ago when the temples had fallen into ruins the present *gadhi* was built so as to cover and conceal the whole platform the limits of which are perhaps marked by the present quadrangle. The portion of its northern face which is still visible testifies to its massive construction and fine carving. Only the hall (*sabhamandapa*) of the main temple has survived but this also was converted into a room by running up walls on three sides of it and an open balcony with domical roof was built upon it. The ceiling and the architraves of the *sabhamandapa* which are still intact bear panels of beautiful carving representing Surya, Siva's dance, Kali, Brahman, Vishnu, Siva and other gods of the Hindu Pantheon. There are also other sculptures some of which can be identified as scenes from the Ramayana and so on.

34. In view of the superb sculpture on the original temple and the dilapidated condition of the *gadhi* which is now a deserted place it was thought desirable to dismantle the modern structures so as to expose to view the existing portion of the original temple, to clear up the jungle, and tidy up the place.

35. The clearance of the jungle and the dismantling of the modern structures were carried out in the year of report. The work of exposing the plinth of the main temple which is buried in earth, of providing drainage, and of tidying the place is in progress.

36. **Suhania.**—Suhania was a large and flourishing town in the mediæval period. It possesses quite a number of ruins of temples both Hindu and Jain dating from the 10th to the 12th century A. C. covering an extensive area round the present village which lies about 30 miles north of Gwalior.

By far the largest and most important of these monuments is a temple of Siva locally known by the name of Kakanmadh. It is popularly believed to have been built by the order of a Queen named Kakanavati from whom the temple derives its name. But a verse in the Sanskrit inscription on the Sasbahu temple on Gwalior Fort records that Kirttiraja, a Kachhawaha King of Gwalior (who reigned about 1000 A. C.), erected a large temple of Siva at Simhapaniya. Simhapaniya is modern Suhania and the temple referred to is obviously the Kakanmadh temple.

37. The temple stands on a ruined and spacious platform which is now completely buried in a mound of earth. The main temple was surrounded by a set of attendant shrines which have now left nothing more than mere traces. The pyramidal roof of the *sabhamandapa* is supported on majestic pillars and the whole exterior of the temple was decorated with fine sculpture. The shrine is surmounted by a spire which rises to a height of nearly 100 feet above the surrounding ground level and is seen from a distance of several miles.

38. The temple is in a much ruined condition. The facing of the *sikhara* has all disappeared. Some of the pillars have disintegrated and portions have flaked off. The roof is damaged and a few lintels have cracked. One and all the attendant shrines have disappeared. The high platform is in ruins and is literally buried in the debris and covered with a jungle of shrubs.

39. As this is one of the finest and largest old temples in this part of the country it is well worthy of being conserved and maintained in permanent good order. This work was sanctioned towards the end of the year, and could only be started when the year under report came to a close.

VI. Upkeep.

40. Annual clearance of jungle and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of conserved monuments.

VII. Exploration. Excavations.

41. No excavations were undertaken in the year of report. The excavations at Pawaya could not be resumed as the necessary procedure for the permanent acquisition of the piece of land in which the excavations have proved fruitful was not completed before the excavation season.

Listing.

42. In the year of report 52 ancient monuments were listed. They are located at 17 different places and comprise ruins of temples, sculptures, memorial pillars, Sati stones, tombs and old guns. Appendix No. C gives a list of these monuments and the more important of them are described below.

43. **Narwar.**—Below the Urwahi gate (western approach) of the Narwar Fort is a Jain temple the present building of which though perhaps hardly two centuries old shelters images of *Tirthankaras* very much older. There are five images in all, four of black and one of white marble. Three of the former are of Neminatha and the fourth perhaps represents Rishabhanatha. This last is the earliest and bears on its pedestal an inscription, dated V. S. 1213. The other three of black marble bear dates V. S. 1316 and 1340 and 1348, respectively. The sculpture of white marble has no inscription.

44. **Narwar Fort.**—This Fort still possesses a number of old guns. Some of these have already been listed. Three more guns were listed this year. The longest of these is that known as *Betwali* lying on the southernmost bastion in the *Gujrat ahata* of the Fort. It is 14 feet and 6 inches long 1 foot and 1½ inches in diameter at the mouth and has a bore of 3 inches diameter. It is numbered 20. Superior in workmanship is another gun called *Jaldar* bearing the number 19. It is placed on the south-west bastion of the *Gujrat ahata*. It is 14 feet in length, 3 feet and 6 inches in circumference at the mouth, the diameter of bore being 4½ inches. The barrel of the gun is decorated with foliage designs incised on it. It is attended by a smaller gun No. 21 lying on the ground close by which is 6 feet and 6 inches in length. The diameter of the barrel at the mouth is 10 inches and that of the bore is 3 inches.

45. **Siroha** (3 miles north-west of Narwar).—This village was visited for a second time in the year of report and a few more antiquities came to my notice during this visit. There are three old images of *Hanumat*, a sculpture of *Agni*, and an intertwined coil of four serpents, lying in front of the temple of a goddess who is popularly called *Anjana*, the mother of *Hanumat*, probably by virtue of the three sculptures of the monkey god which are lying in front of the temple, but who really appears to be the goddess *Parvati* carrying the child *Kartikaya*, or the Jain goddess *Ambika*. There is a round well built of large blocks of stone as usual in the mediæval period. Two old big *Siva Lingas* and two broken sculptures of *Nandi* are lying near the village.

46. **Indhar.**—Indhar is an old village about 20 miles to the south-east of *Kolaras* on the left bank of the river of the same name. Large size bricks and fragments of pottery are found under ground on the western outskirts of the village and traces of brick dwellings and a circular brick well are seen on the banks of the river about a furlong to the north of the village. The place seems to have possessed also a number of Hindu and Jain temples the sites of which marked with fragments of old sculptures are seen along the bank of the river a furlong or two to the north and east of the village. Judging from the fragments, the ruins appear to date from the 8th century onwards. The sculptures seen above ground are detailed in this list (Appendix No. F). But I was told that quite a large number of sculptures are concealed under water in the pool of the river at the *Nayaghat* where people bathe. It would be worth while to make a search for these during a hot season when the water of the river reaches its lowest ebb. The *Haveli* of the *Zamindar*, a temple adjoining it and a temple of goddess in a grove outside the village all built by the grandfather of the present *Zamindar* are good specimens of modern carving work. They are, however, shabbily kept.

47. **Baghoria.**—A village about 4 miles east of Indhar. On the south-west outskirts of the village there are a number of old *sati* stones the inscriptions on which have been obliterated hopelessly. The ruins of a Mohammedan tomb with a few well carved grave stones in the *Chanderi* style stand about a furlong to the north-east of the village. But they are of little interest. It is said that a Mohammedan chief had first settled at this place and later on shifted to *Ranod* which is about 10 miles further east.

District Tawarghar.

48. **Khera.**—On the Morena-Ambah Road near the village Khera about 7 miles from Morena is an old site. Here to the north of the road on a prominence marking the site of an old Hindu temple of about the 10th century is a group of sculptures of goddess Mahishamardini, Ganesa, Surya, Siva and other gods which, though finely carved, are now very badly damaged.

49. **Baydipura.**—In and about the village of Baydipura which is about 3 miles to the north-west of Suhania are scattered a number of old sculptures and architectural pieces mostly brought from the ruins of Suhania. Among one of these groups was a rather good fragment of a sculpture of a woman holding her hands overhead as if in an attitude of shaking off sloth. The feet are broken off. This has since been brought to the Museum.

50. **Rithora.**—Near this village close to the Railway Station of the same name about 16 miles north of Gwalior, on the Gwalior-Bhind line stand a few interesting stone pillars commemorating warriors killed in battle. Four of these are near a well on the eastern outskirts of the village and judging from the deep carving of the fighting scenes on them they may be assigned to the 8th or 9th century A. C. The group of so many contemporary memorial pillars in one place perhaps indicates that they mark the site of a battle.

51. About a furlong to the west of these is another isolated memorial pillar. Close by are the ruins of a temple in which is seen a four-faced stone pillar peculiarly carved. On one of the faces is carved a sword, on another face is a *Trisula*, on the third a bow and arrows, and on the fourth a *Chakra* (?).

District Esagarh.

52. **Mahuwan.**—Mahuwan is an old village about 10 miles to the north of Esagarh. Scattered around it are a number of fragments of Hindu and Jain sculptures, architectural pieces belonging to temples and a few *sati* stones all dating from the 11th century onwards. The sites of some of the temples can yet be traced. But with the exception of a small shrine locally known as Madhi with ruins of a small Nandi pavilion in front, situated about a quarter of a mile to the south-west of the village, none of them is standing. The old name of the place was probably Madhubana.

53. **Deokani.**—This village situated about 3 miles to the south-east of Esagarh was also visited for a second time and some fresh monuments came to light during the search. Near a deserted and dilapidated *gadhi* were found the ruins of about a dozen small shrines standing in a row facing the east. The shrines are severally dedicated to Vishnu, Siva and Devi and may date from the 12th or 13th century A. C. In the ruins are seen two *sati* pillars one of which bears an inscription dated in Samvat 1387. In the front of these shrines is a *baodi* or step-well contemporary with them.

54. About a quarter of a mile to the east of these stands a temple with a shrine and a *sabhamandapa* attached to it, facing to the east. The shrine measures 5 feet by 5 feet 2 inches and the *sabhamandapa* 11 feet 4 inches by 12 feet 1 inch inside. The *sikhara* has fallen. Over the lintel of the shrine door are Brahma, Vishnu and Siva while the pedestal of the idol inside the shrine is empty.

55. A short distance further east is a small shrine also facing to the east. It is called Ganesa Madhi, for on the central (dedicatory) block of the lintel is Ganesa flanked by Brahman at one end and Siva at the other.

56. Flanking this shrine on the left are the traces of another shrine and a memorial pillar is standing near the latter.

57. **Mamon.**—Mamon is a mere hamlet consisting of a few huts of Gujars about 4 miles to the south of Esagarh. Between the huts and the foot of the hill on the west is the old site of the village. Both on the north and south of this site are the ruins of a few mediæval Hindu and Jain temples, the latter predominating.

58. These temples were in three groups. At present only one Jain temple in the southernmost group is standing, but the sites of about half a dozen other temples are visible. The standing temple has a shrine measuring 8'10" by 5'7" internally and facing to the west. There was a porch in front of the shrine. This porch and the *sikhara* of the shrine have disappeared. The basement of the shrine is old but the upper portions of the walls are a later restoration. At present the shrine has no roof. Inside is a big idol of a *Tirthamkara* 8'10" from head to feet. The pedestal is concealed in debris and so the *lanchhana* if any is not seen. The *Tirthamkara* is attended by two *Yakshas* and five other smaller figures of *Tirthamkaras* standing in the shrine. The principal idol which has a halo behind the head, though slightly damaged is on the whole a good specimen of a 10th century sculpture. The lintel of the shrine door frame also bears images of *Tirthamkaras*. Flanking the door on the north is a fine sculpture of seated Parsvanatha. In a niche at the north-west corner of the exterior of the shrine is a sculpture of Ambika and in a corresponding niche at the south-west corner is a sculpture of Chakresvari. A number of broken images of *Tirthamkaras* are lying in the debris.

59. The ruins of other temples may be passed over but a group of Hindu sculptures collected in a rubble enclosure on the site of the old hamlet are worth a mention. Among them are a sculpture of Vishnu, another of Mahishamardini, a third of an eight-armed goddess and a fourth of Brahman. But the most interesting among the lot are three images of women each carrying a lamp. I had never before seen such a representation.* These are worth being preserved in the Museum.

60. About 2 furlongs to the south-east of Mamon stands a small shrine facing to the west and traces of another close by. A sculpture of Siva-Parvati is lying in the ruins.

District Mandasor.

61. **Khilchipura.**—In the village Khilchipura near Mandasor I noticed two small but nicely carved sculptures of *Dvarapalas* (Gupta period) stuck up in the walls of a newly built Jain temple. The trustees of the temple have agreed to the removal of the sculptures to the Museum of Archaeology.

District Ujjain.

62. **Ujjain.**—About a mile to the east of the Ujjain Railway Station, built up in the southern embankment of the Railway line between telegraph

*NOTE—Since this was in type I came across a somewhat similar design of an old brass lamp.

wire posts Nos. $\frac{633}{3}$ and $\frac{633}{4}$ are two big old water spouts of black trap carved into the shape of the heads of *makaras*. Permission has been obtained from the Railway authorities concerned for removing the sculptures to our Museum.

63. Under a tree on a prominence, a short distance to the east of the astronomical observatory are lying two or three old sculptures one of which is a *naga* figure. It is in the form of a human bust with folded hands, the head is shaded under a canopy of serpent's hoods and the lower half of the body is shaped like a serpent's tail. Though considerably damaged, the carving is a specimen of good sculpture and may be taken to the Museum.

64. **Devadungari.**—Devadungari is a small barren hill 13 or 14 miles to the north-west of the Unhel Station on the Ujjain Nagda Section of the B.B. and C. I. Railway. On the southern slope of the hill is a hamlet of a few houses mostly inhabited by the *Pujaris* or caretakers of a local temple.

65. I visited the place with a view to see if it could be identified with Devagiri mentioned by Kalidasa in the *Meghaduta*. On examination of the site I was satisfied that it was the place meant by the poet.

66. My reasons for the identification are:—

- (i) The name of the place, namely, Devadungari, is identical with the name Devagiri, the vernacular word *dungari* being an equivalent of the Sanskrit word *giri* as both mean a hill or mountain.
- (ii) The geographical position of *Devadungri* fits in exactly with that of Devagiri as described by Kalidasa in the *Meghaduta*. For, Devadungari is situated between the two rivers the Gambhir (Gambhira) a tributary of the Sipra, and the Chambal (Charmanvati), on the direct route from Ujjain (Ujjayini) to Mandasor (Dasapura).
- (iii) Kalidasa refers to a temple (abode) of Skanda on the hill Devagiri. Skanda was the generalissimo of the army of gods in their campaign against the demon Taraka. Now one of the two modern temples which crown the summit of the Devadungari hill is sacred to Devadharmaraja who is represented in stone as a warrior god riding a horse and carrying a spear. The attributes of Skanda and Devadharmaraja are so similar that one is justified in recognising in the latter a survival of his prototype the former. (The worship of Skanda survives probably also in the modern cult of Khandoba in Maharashtra who like Devadharmaraja in Malwa is represented as a warrior god riding on a horse). The modern temple of Devadharmaraja on Devadungari hill therefore, very probably marks the site of the ancient temple of Skanda referred to by Kalidasa. It is true that no traces of the old temple such as carved stones are seen on the site to this day. But this is in no way strange; for, a similar fate overtook so many other ancient temples in Malwa in the turbulent and intolerant days of Muhammadan invasions. Old fanes were demolished and their existence was completely effaced by the removal of their material to be used up in buildings elsewhere.

District Bhilsa.,

67. **Badoh.**—Nearly a mile due east of the village Badoh is a group of ruined temples known as Satmarhi or seven shrines. At present only six shrines are standing but the ruins indicate the previous existence of many more. Two shrines only have preserved their door frames one previous of which has the image of Vishnu on the dedicatory block of the lintel and the other has that of Siva. In the former is enshrined a seated idol of the Buddha avatara of Vishnu. A similar but bigger and more elaborately carved sculpture is seen in another (southernmost) of the existing shrines, and a third such sculpture is seen in the ruins of still another shrine. One of the standing shrines has preserved only the pedestal of its idol. From the short fat foot on the pedestal and from the figure of an attendant playing on a tabor which still survive it would appear that the idol which occupied the pedestal was that of Ganesa dancing.

68. **Pathari.**—At the south-west point in the hill between Badoh and Pathari four or five rooms have been built in rough rubble masonry on a high platform against the natural rock. The structures are not very old; carved stones and sculptures brought from the ruins of old temples which abound in the neighbourhood have been utilised in them. In the last but one room from the west a panel 1'10" long by 1'8" broad containing the figures of the Seven Mothers and Siva is cut in the living rock which serves as the back wall of the room. Close to the panel of sculptures is an inscription in 10 lines of Gupta characters (5th century A. C.) engraved on a tablet in the same rock and recording the excavation of the sculptures.

VIII. Epigraphy.

69. Sixteen inscriptions were copied or noticed in the year of report. Out of these thirteen are in Sanskrit, two are in Hindi and one is partly in Arabic and partly in Persian. Classified according to ruling dynasties, one of the inscriptions refers itself to a local chief or Maharaja of the country round about Bhilsa, probably a tributary of the Gupta Empire, one to the Paramaras of Dhar, one to the Jajapellas of Narwar, one to the Tughlaqs and another to the Surs of Delhi, and the remaining mention no king or ruler.

70. The earliest of these is an inscription engraved on a rock tablet in a hill between Badoh and Pathari (District Bhilsa). The characters are Gupta, the language Sanskrit and the object of the inscription is to record the excavation of a panel of sculptures of the Sapta Matrikas or Seven Mothers near which the inscription is engraved. The inscription mentions Maharaja Jayatsena who is styled—Vishayesvara (Lord of the District). But the inscription being badly damaged owing to the peeling off of the rock the name of the District is lost. The date was recorded but is lost with the exception of words showing the day of the month which in this case is the 13th day of the bright half. It is likewise not certain whether the inscription dates from the reign of Maharaja Jayatsena or goes down to that of one of his descendants as the words following *Jayatsenasya* are missing.

71. The next in date is the stone inscription found in a *Dhimar's* house near the Chatua Darwaza at Udaypur (District Bhilsa). It is in Nagari characters and 27 lines of Sanskrit verse engraved on a complete stone slab. This is the latter half of the inscription known as Udaypur *prasasti*

the first half of which on another slab was found at Udaypur and published 34 years ago in the *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. I, pp. 222 ff. Owing to good many abrasions which the stone has undergone a major portion of the inscription has become obliterated and undecipherable. In the first line it eulogises the military exploits of the Paramara king Udayaditya and specially mentions the total destruction (*samhara*) of the king of Dahila or Chedi (*Dahiladhisa*) at his hands. The genealogy of the Paramaras stops here with Udayaditya. Next follows the panegyric of the family of Nemaks. The names cannot be made out clearly owing to the imperfect condition of the stone. The object of the inscription would appear to be to record the construction of a temple or temples by a scion of the Nemaka family. No date is given. Thus the inscription adds very little to the historical information which we already possess from the first half of this *prasasti* already published.

72. The third in chronological order is a stone inscription originally coming from Barah in the Narwar District and now in the possession of Mr. B. R. Bhalerao. The inscription is on a fragment of stone and forms the concluding portion of a *prasasti* recording the construction of a temple of Vishnu by (name lost). Then follow a few names of traders (*vanik*) by caste who were partners in the work. The names of the engravers (*sutradhara*) and the composer (*kavi*) are given as Sthirarkka and Narayana. At the end the date V. S. 1098 is given in figures.

73. The next in importance would be the stone inscription found built up in a vegetable vendor's (*kurjda's*) house at Narwar. This inscription is in Nagari characters and consists of 18 lines of Sanskrit verse incised on a slab of stone. The stone is complete but the record is left unfinished by the engraver. Further a large irregular patch of the inscribed surface has peeled off owing to which only a portion of the inscription is decipherable. The inscription records the genealogy of the Jajapellas of Narwar down to Asalladeva. Then it describes a family of Mathura Kayasthas originally coming from Gopagiri (Gwalior). The founder of the family was Bhuvanapala who is described as having been a minister of King Bhoja of Dhara. His son was Vasudeva and the latter's son Damodara whose wife was a daughter of Pithana. This couple had five sons the eldest of whom was (name lost). The inscription closes with the panegyric of this man.

74. One more Sanskrit inscription discovered this year is of interest. It is recorded on a memorial pillar lying in the ruins of a series of small shrines in front of a ruined *garhi* (fort) near the deserted village of *Deokani (District Esagarh). It records the death of Rauta Sahajana-deva in a fight over the kidnapping of cows (*go-graha yudhitah*) and the *sahagamana* of his wives in V. S. 1387 during the reign of Mahmood Tughlaq of Delhi. What is interesting in this inscription is that it explains the relation between the panels representing a row of cows and a scene of fight, often met with on memorial pillars of warriors killed on battle fields. The explanation is that these fights took place over attempts to kidnap cows (Cf. *Uttaragograhana* in the *Mahabharata*). This representation of cows on memorial pillars was a puzzle to me till it was solved by this inscription which showed its connection with

*NOTE—See page 9, para 53 above.

the scene of fight depicted. The other Sanskrit inscriptions are mostly votive or *sati* records and are of no special importance.

75. The Arabic-Persian inscription found in debris at Narwar Fort records the construction of a mosque (at Narwar) by Dilawar Khan who styles himself as a Viceroy of Mahmood Shah Adil (of the Sur Dynasty of Delhi) in A. H. 960-1522 A. C.

76. An analysis of all the inscriptions is given in Appendix No. D.

IX. Numismatics.

77. In all 941 coins were examined during the year of report out of which one was of gold, 690 of silver and 250 of copper. The pre-Muhammadan coins included two silver punch-marked pieces and 250 copper coins commonly known as Gadhia which are a debased imitation of Indo-Sessianian coinage. The Muhammadan coins comprised one gold Mohar of Akbar the Great, dated A. H. 981, one silver coin of Nadir Shah and the rest were silver coins of the later Mughal Emperors of Delhi. The mints represented are Allahabad, Balwant Nagar, Kora, Ahmedabad, Surat, Seronj, Etawah and Alamgirpur (Bhilsa). The gold coin was purchased, 419 silver coins were received as treasure-trove finds from three different places in the State, while 271 silver and 250 copper coins were received from the Central Treasury where they had been lying for some years. For a list of coins examined see Appendix No. E.

78. A change in the procedure of dealing with coins found as treasure-trove in the State was sanctioned by the Council of Regency. Hitherto the surplus coins in the treasure-trove finds used to be sent through the Resident at Gwalior to the Superintendent in charge of the Archaeological section of the Indian Museum, Calcutta, who examined and distributed them as necessary among the different Museums in British India and returned the rest. In future the examination and distribution of treasure-trove finds will be done by this Department.

X. Museum.

79. Seven stone sculptures, three stone inscriptions, eighteen metal images, four copper-plates inscriptions, twenty-eight old paintings and one hundred and thirty-seven coins, or one hundred and ninety-seven antiquities in all were acquired for the Archaeological Museum, in the year of report. All the stone sculptures and stone inscriptions and two copper plates were collected from different places in the State. Two copper plate inscriptions were received from the Office of the Law Member, 20 silver, 3 billon and 6 copper coins were received in exchange from Mr. Jaisuriya of Ceylon, and 125 coins were acquired from the treasure-trove. One gold coin, 18 metal images and 28 old paintings were purchased.

80. Among these acquisitions, the three stone inscriptions, namely, (1) the second slab of the Udaypur *prasasti* of the Paramara king Udayaditya, (2) the incomplete inscription of the reign of Asalladeva of Narwar and (3) the Arabic Persian inscription of the reign of Muhammad Shah Adil of Delhi, two copper plate grants from Kuretha in Tawarghar District, one of Malayavarman a Pratihara king of Gwalior and the other of his brother Nrivarman, dated in V. S.

1277 and 1304 respectively and described in the *Annual Administration Report* of Samvat 1972 (year 1915-16), the gold Mohar of Akbar, the tantric image of ten-headed and multi-armed Siva, the image of a goddess riding a lion and the two images of Bodhisattvas are of historical, iconographic or artistic interest. Among the coins received in exchange and added to the Museum are a silver coin of Menander, one of Siladitya, a tribal copper coin from Taxila, one of Azes I, two of Azes II and two of Kadphises, two billon coins of Ranjubala and one Kushan coin. The detailed list of antiquities added to the Archæological Museum is set forth in Appendix No. F.

81. One hundred and fourteen European and 608 Indian visitors have recorded their signatures in the Visitors' Book at the Archæological Museum though many more must have actually visited the institution.

82. The following were some of the distinguished visitors. Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians, H. H. the Maharaja of Baroda, the Chief of Jamkhandi, Maharani Sahiba of Satara, Atiya Begum of Bombay, Sir M. Visvesvarayya, Rao Bahadur C. V. Vaidya, Prof. Dr. J. Ph. Vogel of Holland, Mr. S. Fyzee Rahamin of Bombay and Mr. Jaisuriya of Ceylon.

XI. Photography.

83. Ninety-nine photographic negatives and forty-two lantern slides were prepared in the year, lists of which appear in Appendices G and H. Besides the prints for record in Office and for illustrating the resume of work contributed to the All-India *Archæological Survey Report* more than 300 prints were prepared for sale to Dr. A. K. Coomaraswamy of the Boston Museum and to Dr. Prof. J. Ph. Vogel of Holland. An album of important photographs of the year was prepared for being submitted to the Council of Regency. Another album was prepared for being presented to Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians during their visit to Gwalior and a third for being submitted to His Highness the Maharaja Sahib as an humble and loyal coronation present from the Department.

XII. Office Library.

84. Ninety-nine books and journals on History, Architecture, Art and allied subjects were added to Office Library in the year of report. Out of these fifty were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due. The list of books is given in Appendix I.

XIII. Income and Expenditure.

85. Statements of income and expenditure of the Department under different heads during the year of report are set forth in Appendices J and K from which it will be seen that the annual expenditure was Rs. 36,066-4-11 including part of the special grant for repairs to certain monuments on the Narwar Fort, sanctioned already. The income amounted to Rs. 214-2-0.

XIV. Important Events.

86. On the auspicious occasion of the Coronation of His Highness the Maharaja Sahib Scindia a beautiful album was submitted as an humble and loyal present from the Department.

87. Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians visited the Museum and other archaeological monuments on the Gwalior Fort when a picture album prepared by the Department was presented as a memento to Their Majesties by His Highness the Maharaja Sahib.

88. His Highness the Maharaja Sahib of Baroda visited the Archaeological Museum.

89. The Department was At Home to His Highness. The Resident, the Members of the Majlis-i-Am, the principal Officers and gentry of Gwalior were among the guests. Owing to a slight indisposition His Highness was not able to attend the function. Mr. L. M. Crump, the Resident at Gwalior, was therefore in the Chair. A brief account of the work accomplished by the Department during the last ten years was read and printed copies were distributed among the guests. A magic lantern show was also given illustrating important archaeological monuments in the State.

XV. Concluding Remarks.

90. In conclusion I am grateful to Sir Appaji Rao Sahib Shitole, K. C. S. I., Amir-ul-Umra, etc., the Offg. Home Member, for the keen interest which he is taking in the work of this Department. I also beg to thank Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar for the unfailing courtesy and valuable advice with which he continued to favour me with regard to the discharge of my official duties, till he proceeded on a long leave.

M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent of Archaeology,
Gwalior State.

APPENDIX No. A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent for the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.**

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.
October 1925.	
25th	Gwalior to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Narwar.
26th	Halt at Narwar.
27th	Narwar to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Gwalior.
November 1925.	
11th-12th	Gwalior to Bareth.
12th	Bareth to Udaypur and back.
"	Bareth to Bina.
12th-13th	Bina to Mhow.
14th	Mhow to Bagh.
15th-18th	Halt at Bagh.
19th	Bagh to Mhow.
20th	Mhow to Mandasor.
21st	Mandasor to Bhilsa.
22nd	Bhilsa to Sanchi and back.
23rd	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
24th	Bhilsa to Bareth.
"	Bareth to Udaypur and back.
25th	Bareth to Gwalior.
December 1925.	
18th	
January 1926.	
17th	On leave.
18th-19th	Bombay to Hospet <i>via</i> Hubli.
20th	Hospet to Hampi.
21st	Halt at Hampi.
22nd	Hampi to Hospet.
22nd-23rd	Hospet to Bombay.
24th	Bombay to Aurangabad.
25th	Aurangabad to Ellora Caves.
26th	Halt at Ellora Caves.
27th	Ellora caves to Daulatabad.
"	Daulatabad to Manmad.
27th-28th	Manmad to Gwalior.
March 1926.	
27th	Gwalior to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Narwar.
28th to 3rd April	Halt at Narwar.
4th	Narwar to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Gwalior.
27th	Gwalior to Morena.
"	Morena to Kunwari river and back.
28th	Morena to Ambah.
29th	Ambah to Suhania.
30th	Suhania to Padhavali.

APPENDIX No. A — (concl'd.)

Date month and year.	Movements and Halts.
May 1926.	
1st ...	Padhavali to Rithora.
" ...	Rithora to Gwalior.
6th ...	Gwalior to Kalhar.
7th ...	Kalhar to Badoh.
8th ...	Badoh to Udaypur.
9th ...	Halt at Udaypur.
10th ...	Udaypur to Bareth.
" ...	Bareth to Ujjain.
11th ...	Ujjain to Unhel.
12th ...	Unhel to Devadungari and back.
" ...	Unhel to Mandasor.
13th-15th ...	Halt at Mandasor.
16th ...	Mandasor to Mhow.
17th ...	Mhow to Sardarpur.
18th ...	Sardarpur to Bagh.
19th ...	Bagh to Bagh Caves.
20th ...	Bagh Caves to Bagh.
21st ...	Bagh to Mhow.
22nd-23rd ...	Mhow to Ujjain.
23rd-24th ...	Ujjain to Bhilsa.
24th ...	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
25th ...	Bhilsa to Gwalior.
June 1926.	
2nd ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
3rd ...	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back.
4th ...	Shivpuri to Kolaras.
5th ...	Kolaras to Indhar.
6th ...	Indhar to Ranod.
7th ...	Halt at Ranod.
8th ...	Ranod to Mahuwan.
9th ...	Mahuwan to Esagarh and thence to Mamon.
10th ...	Mamon to Maholi.
11th ...	Maholi to Chanderi.
12th ...	Chanderi to Mungaoli.
12th-13th ...	Mungaoli to Gwalior.
16th ...	Gwalior to Rithora.
" ...	Rithora to Padhavli.
17th ...	Padhavli to Rithora.
" ...	Rithora to Gwalior.
Officiating Superintendent's Diary of Tour for Samvat 1982.	
December 1925.	
18th ...	Gwalior to Bareth.
19th ...	Bareth to Udaypur.
20th ...	Udaypur to Badoh.
21st ...	Badoh to Udaypur.
22nd ...	Udaypur to Bareth.
23rd ...	Bareth to Bhilsa.
24th ...	Bhilsa to Ujjain.
25th ...	Ujjain to Mandasor.
26th ...	Mandasor to Sondni.
27th ...	Halt at Sondni.
28th ...	Sondni to Mandasor.
29th-31st ...	Halt at Mandasor.
June 1926.	
1st ...	Mandasor to Ujjain.
2nd ...	Ujjain to Gwalior.

APPENDIX No. B.
Statement of Expenditure on Monuments conserved during Samvat 1982.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of Monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		Total.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total.	REMARKS.
			Current year.	Last year.		Current year.	Last year.		
1	Gwalior Fort	...	Rs.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	
2	Bagh	Gujari Mahal	182	...	182 0 0	156 9 9	...	156 9 9	
3	Udaypur	Bagh Caves	1,000	556 10 6	1,556 10 6	175 9 0	...	175 9 0	
4	Padhavli	Udayesvar Temple	2,142	134 12 9	2,276 12 9	2,133 15 9	134 2 0	2,268 1 9	
5	Subania	Temple in Gadhi	420	...	420 0 0	420 0 0	...	420 0 0	
6	Mandasor Fort.	Kakanmadh Temple	2,413	...	2,413 0 0	9 8 0	...	9 8 0	
7	Sondani	A. Gupta Sculpture	320	670 0 0	990 0 0	317 9 9	656 12 6	974 6 3	
8	Do.	Yasodharman Pillars	...	3,021 0 0	3,021 0 0	...	3,018 12 8	3,018 12 8	
9	Khilchipura	Inscription stone	...	150 0 0	150 0 0	...	103 5 6	103 5 6	
10	Narwar	Torana Pillar	...	352 0 0	352 0 0	...	327 15 7	327 15 7	
11	Badoli	Jait Khambha	...	102 5 9	102 5 9	...	87 2 9	87 2 9	
12	Do.	Sola Khambhi	...	11 6 6	11 6 6	...	11 0 6	11 0 6	
13	Do.	Jain Temple	...	9 5 6	9 5 6	...	9 0 0	9 0 0	
14	Narwar	Gadarmal Temple	...	12 14 6	12 14 6	...	12 0 0	12 0 0	
15	Gwalior Fort	Narwar Fort	...	13,906 15 0	13,906 15 0	...	11,698 0 9	11,698 0 9	
16	Chanderi	Notice Board near Museum Building. Providing descriptive inscriptions to minor monuments.	83	...	83 0 0	82 14 6	...	82 14 6	
		TOTAL	6,560	18,935 6 6	25,495 6 6	3,296 2 9	16,068 4 3	19,632 7 0	

APPENDIX NO. C.

Monuments listed during the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality.	Name of monument.	Class.	Ownership.
District Narwar.				
1	Narwar.	Jain temple below the Urwabi gate of the Fort	III	Jain community.
2	"	An old Baodi on the Magroni road with inscription dated Samvat 1822 ...	III	
3	" Fort.	A gun known as Jaldar	I	
4	" "	Another smaller gun lying close to above.	I	
5	" "	" gun known as Betvali ...	I	
6	Siroha.	A group of old sculptures in front of the temple to Anjana	III	
7	"	An old round stone built well ...	III	
8	"	Two big Siva <i>lingas</i> and two broken Nandins	III	
9	"	Some fragments of Jain images ...	III	
10	Indhar.	Several sites of old Hindu and Jain temples marked with old carved stone fragments	III	
11	"	A memorial pillar inscribed, at the western entrance of the village	II	
12	"	A group of sculptures on the bank of the river near the Naya ghat ...	III	
13	"	Another group of sculptures placed on a <i>kachcha</i> platform in the north east portion of the village	III	
14	"	A big idol of standing Jain <i>Tirthankara</i> in the bed of the river about $\frac{1}{4}$ mile to the north east of the village ...	III	
15	"	Traces of old buildings and a circular brick well on the bank of the river close to the above	III	
16	"	A badly damaged but remarkable Jain sculpture in a lane in the western part of the village... ..	III	
17	Baghoria.	<i>Sati</i> stones outside the village, on the south west of it	III	
18	"	A ruined Muhammadan tomb outside the village, on the north east of it ...	III	
District Tonwarghar.				
19	Khera.	A group of sculptures lying on the site of an 11th century temple	III	
20	Baodipura.	Sculptures placed on a <i>kachcha</i> platform outside the village (one furlong to the north)	III	
21	Rithora.	A memorial pillar in a field to the south of village	III	
22	"	Site of an old temple marked by carved architectural pieces	III	
District Esagarh.				
23	Mahuwan	A shrine known as Madhi	III	
24	"	Three shrines and a sculpture of Kubera on a small <i>tila</i> on the bank of the river.	III	
25	"	A big roof slab of an old shrine ...	III	
26	"	Two <i>sati</i> stones one bearing an inscription dated Samvat 1443	III	
27	"	Site of another shrine	III	

APPENDIX No. C.—(concl'd.)

No.	Locality.	Name of monument.	Class.	Ownership.
28	Mahuwan.	A big sculpture of Hanumat and other smaller fragments ...	III	
29	"	A seated Jain <i>Tirthankara</i>	III	
30	"	Another smaller <i>Tirthankara</i> half buried in earth	III	
31	"	Ruins of another shrine with a <i>Siva linga</i> on pedestal and a sculpture of <i>Mahishamardini</i>	III	
32	"	A sculpture of <i>Ganesa</i> half buried in earth close by... ..	III	
33	"	A <i>sati</i> stone inscribed (Samvat 1724) ...	III	
34	Deokani.	Ruins of several old shrines near a deserted <i>gadhi</i> about a mile to the east of the old temple of goddess	III	
35	"	An inscribed <i>sati</i> pillar dated Samvat 1387 among the ruins	III	
36	"	An old <i>bardi</i> known as <i>Sas Bahu ki bardi</i> .	III	
37	"	Another old shrine about $\frac{1}{4}$ mile further east	III	
38	"	A small shrine known as <i>Ganesa madhi</i> still further east	III	
39	"	A memorial pillar and ruins of another shrine close by	III	
40	Mamon.	A Jain temple and ruins of some others with fragments of sculptures and carved architectural pieces lying about in the ruins (group I)	II	
41	"	Site of another group of old temples further north	III	
42	"	Site of a third group of old temples to the east of above	III	
43	"	A collection of sculptures (Hindu and Jain) in a rough rubble enclosure in the ruins of the old village	III	
44	"	Two old broken memorial pillars with inscriptions	III	
45	"	An old stone built well	III	
46	"	A small ruined <i>Siva</i> shrine about $\frac{1}{4}$ mile to the south east of the hamlet ...	III	
District Mandasor.				
47	Khilchipura.	Two small old sculptures of <i>Dvarapalas</i> (?) built in the wall of a modern Jain temple.	II	
District Ujjain.				
48	Deo dongri or Devadungri.	The hill referred to as <i>Devagiri</i> in <i>Kalidasa's meghaduta</i> identified ...	III	
49	Ujjain.	Two big carved water spouts built into the Rail Road	II	
50	"	Two or three old sculptures lying under a tree near the astronomical Observatory.	III	
District Bhilsa				
51	Badoh.	Ruins of a group of temples known as <i>satmadhi</i>	III	
52	Pathari.	Images of mothers (<i>Sapta matrikas</i>) with an inscription all carved in rock in front of which a structural room has been built in later times	II	

APPENDIX No. D.

List of Inscriptions copied or noticed during the Year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purport.	REMARKS.
1	Narwar.	A stone slab built as a thresh-old in a <i>kujda</i> * house.	18	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	Asalla of Narwar.	<p>The inscription is left incomplete by the engraver. Verse 22 has been finished and a word or two of the next verse bring the last line to a close. Further the engraved portion is seriously damaged by weathering and a wholesale peeling off of the surface of the stone. Hence the existing portion also is only partly decipherable. It opens with the words ॐ गणपति प्रसादात्. After invoking a blessing, it proceeds to describe the genealogy of the local kings (of the Jajpalla dynasty) and brings it down to Asalla whose father and predecessor नृवर्मन् is extolled as having exacted a tribute even from the proud king of Dhara.</p> <p>Next it gives the genealogy of a family of माधुर काश्य originally coming from गोपगिरि दुर्ग (Gwalior). The founder's name is mentioned as सुवन्पाळ who was a minister of king भोज of चार. His son was वासुदेव and his son दामोदर whose wife wasdaughter of वीरन. This couple had five sons, of whom the eldest was.....A panegyric of this man brings the existing portion of the inscription to a close.</p>	

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd).

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
2	Narwar.	On a loose stone slab found in debris in the compound of the Dargah of Madar Shah on Narwar Fort.	10 and $\frac{1}{2}$ on left margin.	Naksh & Nastaliq.	Arabic & Persian.	A.H. 960 = 1552 A.C.	Mohammed Shah of Dehli.	The Arabic portion is mere quotations from the <i>Koran</i> and <i>Hadith</i> . The Persian portion records the construction of a mosque by Dilawar Khan who styles himself Viceroy of Mohammed Shah Adil (of Dehli) in A. H. 960. It also gives names of the composer, writer and engraver as Syed Ahmad, Nazir Shattari (a follower of Mohammed Ghous) and Khanjahan respectively.	
3	"	On the pedestal of a <i>तीर्थंकर</i> in a Jain temple at western foot of the Narwar Fort.	...	Nagari.	...	V.S. 1213	...	Records the installation of the idol सं० १२१३ आषाढ सुदी [९].	
4	"	" another image	...	"	...	V.S. 1316	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३१६ उद्युष्ट बदी २ सोमे.	
5	"	" another.	...	"	...	V.S. 1340	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३४० वैशाख सुदी ७ सोमे.	
6	"	" "	...	...	...	V.S. 1348	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३४८ वैशाख सुदी १५ शनी.	
7	"	In a <i>Bardi</i> on the Magroni Road	10 and $\frac{1}{2}$ on left margin.	Nagari.	Hindi.	V.S. 1822 Saka 1687	...	Records the construction of the well during the reign of Sri Rama Simha Kachhava of Narwar on Saturday the 7th of the bright half of वैशाख in V. S. 1822 Saka 1687.	

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd.)

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purport.	REMARKS.
8	Bara.	On a stone slab now in the possession of Mr. B. K. Bhalerao.	8	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	V.S. 1098	...	The inscription is fragmentary being the ending portion of a <i>प्रशस्ति</i> . The existing portion is well preserved and can be completely read. It records the construction of a temple of Vishnu (<i>Garudasana</i>) by—(name lost) then follows a list of names of traders (<i>वर्तिक</i>) by caste who were partners in the work. The names of the <i>सूत्रकार</i> (engraver) and the <i>कवि</i> (composer) are given as <i>स्थिरार्क</i> and <i>नारायण</i> respectively. The date is given in figures at the end.	
9	Indhar.	On a memorial pillar half buried at the western entrance of the village.	7	"	"	V.S. 1345	...	Purport not made out.	The inscription is weathered and could not be properly deciphered from the stone during the short visit.
10	Mahuwan	On a <i>Sati</i> post.	...	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	V.S. 1443	...	Do.	Easily weathered
11	"	On another <i>Sati</i> post.	...	"	Hindi.	V.S. 1724	...	Do.	Do.

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd).

RELARBS.

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purport.
12	Deokani.	On a <i>Sati</i> pillar.	10	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	S. 1387.	Mahamood.	Records the सहगमन of the two wives of सहजन देव who was killed in a fight over the kidnapping of cows on the 14th of the dark half of Phalguna Samvat 1387. Mentions कौ [र] सीह in the 2nd line and भीरदेव in the third.
13	Mamon.	On a fragment of a memorial pillar.	3	"	"	S...5	...	 Owing to the damaged condition of the inscription only a few letters here and there can be deciphered. The purport cannot therefore be made out clearly.
14	"	On another.	9	"	"	S. 1351	Maharaja	
15	Pathari.	On a tablet in rock near a panel of sculptures representing the <i>Sapta Matikas</i> .	9	Gupta.	"	Words or figures showing year and month are lost. 13th day of the bright fortnight	Jayat-sena.	But probably the object of the inscription is to record the engraving of the idols of the Seven Mothers in the panel in the rock near which the inscription is incised. Lines 6 and 7 contained the date of which the words or figures showing the year and month are lost. At the beginning of line 7 the words शुद्ध दिवसे त्रयोदश्यां are preserved. Further in the same line are seen the words भगवत्सो मातरः Line 8 contains the words विषयेभ्यस्तत्र महाराज जयसेनस्य which appears to show that either Jayatsena or one of his descendants was the then reigning chief.

Badly damaged and not completely decipherable.
Do.

APPENDIX No. D.—(concl'd.)

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
16	Udaypur.	On a loose stone slab found in a house near Chatma Gate.	27	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	Not given.	Udayaditya Paramara	<p>This inscription is the latter half of the Udaypur <i>prasasti</i> of the reign of Udayaditya, the first half of which was found several years ago and published in the <i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. I, pp. 222 ff. The inscription is badly worn out and has therefore not been completely deciphered. The genealogy of the Paramara kings ends with the reign of Udayaditya only. In the course of the eulogy of Udayaditya it records his several military exploits among which his complete destruction of the king of Dabala (<i>दहला</i>) in line 2 is worthy of note. Then follows the panegyric of the family of Nemakas whom the king had put in charge of the town of Udaypur. Owing to the imperfect decipherment of the inscription so far, it has not become possible but it appears from some of the expressions and phrases that have been deciphered that it records the construction of a temple or temples by Damodara a scion of the Nemaka family. No date has been recorded in the inscription. So the new find does not add much to the historical information which we already possess about the Paramaras.</p>	

APPENDIX No. E.

Coins examined during the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Name of king.	Metal.	No. of coins examined.	Remarks.
Pre-Muhammadan Coins.				
1	Punch-marked	Silver.	2	Of <i>I. M. C.</i> Vol. I, plate XIX, 3.
2	Gadhin pieces (mediæval dyanasties of Northern and Western India) ...	Copper.	250	<i>Ibid.</i> Plate XXXVI
Muhammadan Coins.				
3	Akbar the Great	Gold.	1	
4	" "	Silver.	1	
5	Shah Jahan	"	2	
6	Aurangzeb	"	43	
7	Shah Alam I	"	8	
8	Jahandar Shah	"	1	
9	Farrukhsiyar	"	29	
10	Rafi-ul-darjat	"	1	
11	Shahjahan II	"	2	
12	Muhammad Shah	"	184	
13	Nadir Shah	"	1	
14	Almad Shah	"	5	
15	Alamgir II	"	10	
16	Shah Alam II	"	368	
17	Bhopal State	"	20	
18	Mutilated	"	13	
		Total.	941	

APPENDIX No. F.

List of antiquities added to the Archaeological Museum during
the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
Stone Sculptures			Ht. Br.	
1	Suhania.	A woman (feet broken off) ...	2'1" × 9"	
2	"	A head of a woman ...	6½" × 6"	
3	"	Another head of a woman ...	5" × 5½"	
4	Narwar.	A canopy of a Jain image flanked on either side by an elephant.	3'1" × 1'5"	
5	Gohad	A <i>chakra-vyuha</i> ...	3' × 3'	
6	Indhar.	A small image of Balarama ...	1'2" × 6"	
7	Surwaya.	A human skull ...	4"	
Stone Inscriptions.				
8	Udaypur.	A Sanskrit inscription ...	2'7" × 2'5"	
9	Narwar.	" " ...	2'2" × 2'	
10	"	A Persian " ...	2'3" × 1'6"	
Metal Images.				
11		An elephant with drums being played on by a rider.	3½" × 3"	Pur- chased.
12		An ornamental lamp with a figure of Gaja-Gauri on the back and horse-men at sides.	6½" × 5"	
13		A standing goddess holding an object perhaps a bell in her right hand.	7½" × 3½"	"
14		A standing goddess holding an object (a flower bud) in left hand.	7" × 2½"	"
15		A standing goddess holding a lotus flower in right hand.	4½" × 2"	"
16		A four armed god (perhaps Siva?) with arrow and sword in right hands and a bow and club in left hands and a garland of skulls round the neck and flanked by a male and female attendant.	8½" × 5¾"	"
17		Hanuman shaped handle of a bell ...	5½" × 1¾"	"
18		A horseman piercing a wild animal (conventional tiger) with a lance.	5" × 2" × 3½"	"
19		A <i>Bodhisattva</i> in <i>dhyani mudra</i> ...	6¾" × 4¾"	"
20		A bull (Nandi) ...	3¾" × 4"	"

APPENDIX No. F.—(contd.)

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
21		A quadruped (perhaps a mouse with a seat on back for an idol).	3 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	Purchased.
22		A devotee seated with folded hands ...	3 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
23		A <i>tantric</i> image with 10 heads and sixty hands, standing.	1'8" × 1'1 $\frac{1}{4}$ "	"
24		A seated image of Vajrapani <i>Bodhi-sattva</i> .	1'1" × 9 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
25		A four armed goddess seated on a lion.	1' $\frac{1}{2}$ " × 5"	"
26		An ornamental duck	8" × 7 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
27		A horse	1' × 8 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
28		A swing supported by two elephants.	11 $\frac{1}{2}$ " × 7 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
Copper-plates.				
29		A grant of land dated Samvat 1719.	7" × 5 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	Received from Muntazim Jagirdaran Office.
30		A grant of land dated Samvat 1740.	7" × 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
31	Kuretha.	Copper-plate inscription of Malayavarman dated Vikrama Samvat 1277.	1'2" × 10 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	
32	"	Copper plate grant of Nrivarman dated Vikrama Samvat 1304.	11 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 7 $\frac{3}{8}$ "	
Old Paintings.				
33		A woman doing her toilet ...	9 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 7 $\frac{1}{4}$ "	Purchased.
34		A picture of the month of Chaitra showing hero and heroine (Krishna and Radha?) seated facing each other flowers in hand.	8 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
35		A picture of the month of Vaisakha. Hero and heroine seated outside a bungalow, flowers in hand, attended by a maid servant holding a fan.	"	"
36		A picture of the month of Jyeshtha. hero and heroine seated in a bungalow in the midst of a garden attended by a maid servant bearing a fan.	8 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 6"	"
37		A picture of the month of Ashadha. hero and heroine standing outside a bungalow. The hero holding the left hand of the heroine with his right. The heroine pointing a finger of her right hand up to clouds in the sky.	8 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 6"	"
38		A picture of the month of Margasirsha. The hero and heroine standing outside a bungalow. The hero is offering flowers to the heroine who also is holding a bunch of flowers in her right hand. A maid servant is preparing a bed inside the bungalow.	"	"

APPENDIX No. F.—(contd.)

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
39		A picture of the month of Pausha. The hero and heroine attended by a maid servant warming their hands on a fire in an open bungalow	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 6''$	Purchased.
40		The hero and heroine riding a trotting camel in a mountainous tract of country, accompanied by a horseman. A footman with fiddle in hand walking in advance. The heroine is shooting an arrow at one of two horsemen seen beyond a hillock in the rear ...	$1' \times 11\frac{1}{4}'' \times 9\frac{3}{4}''$	"
41		The hero and heroine on horse back. The hero pointing out his hand towards the rear	$9\frac{1}{2}'' \times 7\frac{1}{4}''$	"
42		Two chiefs seated on two separate carpets facing each other. The senior chief advising and the junior listening	$8'' \times 6\frac{1}{4}''$	"
43		An Emperor and Empress on horse back. A hawk on the Emperor's hand. (Baz Bahadur and Rupamati ?).	$10\frac{1}{4}'' \times 9\frac{1}{2}''$	"
44		A boar hunt. A horseman wounding a boar with his sword	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 5\frac{1}{2}''$	"
45		Two ladies seated facing each other. One smoking a <i>hukkah</i> and the other playing on a lute (<i>tambora</i>) ...	$6\frac{1}{2}'' \times 11\frac{1}{4}''$	"
46		A Rajput chief seated on a throne sword in hand	$10' \times 8''$	"
47		Picture of Asavari a Ragini of Sriruga showing a man and a woman seated facing each other outside a house in a garden. The woman is holding a cobra in either hand and the man is playing on a flute	$10'' \times 7\frac{3}{4}''$	"
48		A blind Emperor (Shah Alam II ?) seated on a throne attended by a chowri-bearer at the back and another servant in front	$11\frac{3}{4}'' \times 8\frac{3}{4}''$	"
49		A picture of Bilawal a Ragini of Hindol Raga showing a heroine seated on a coach and putting on ear jewels. A maid servant in front showing her a looking glass	$10'' \times 7\frac{3}{4}''$	"
50		A picture of Purvi a Ragini of Dipaka Raga. A heroine seated on a pedestal and attended by two maid servants with folded hands	$11'' \times 7\frac{3}{4}''$	"

APPENDIX No. F.—(concl'd.)

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks
51		A picture of Soratha Raga. Heroine seated in her <i>mahal</i> arranging her hair. A maid servant seated in front showing a looking glass. Another maid servant standing at the back holding articles of toilet (?) ...	10" × 6½"	Purchased.
52		A picture of Malasari a Ragini of Bhairava Raga. Heroine seated on a pedestal in a garden house and conversing with a maid ...	10½" × 7¾"	"
53		A picture of Malakansa Raga. Hero and heroine seated on a coach in a <i>mahal</i> , attended by four maids bearing <i>chouri</i> and <i>pandan</i> and other objects	8" × 10"	"
54		A <i>fakir</i> seated on a mattress, telling beads of a rosary. Another seated facing him	7¾" × 5"	"
55		A saint wearing a <i>Ramanandi safa</i> is seated leaning against a cushion and telling on a rosary	10" × 8"	"
56		A heroine seated on a cushion, a maid servant standing in front flowers in hand (?)	11" × 7"	"
57		On a raised platform outside a bungalow on the bank of a tank a goddess (?) is seated on a tiger skin. Another goddess (?) is standing near her with her hands on a swing. Another woman is sitting behind her. A king with folded hands is sitting in front. Five other chiefs are standing down below. A <i>sadhu</i> accompanied by a dog is also standing close by. ...	11¾" × 9¼"	Purchased.
58		A hunting scene. An Emperor riding an elephant and party hunting two wild boars. A number of attendants on foot and horse back are moving about in the jungle and shooting arrows	1'2" × 11½"	"
59		A Maratha Raja of Tonjore (Sarfoji?) is seated on a mattress leaning against a <i>lod</i>	8¾" × 6¾"	"
60		Mirza Sidu Sahib is riding on a horse followed by four Sardars also on horse back. Three soldiers on foot are at the head of the cavalcade ...	1'7¼" × 1'11½"	"
Old Coins.				
61-197		Old coins	137	

APPENDIX No. G.

List of photo negatives made during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Cave No. 3, after clearance ...	Quarter	
2	"	" " " " another view	"	
District Bhilsa.				
3	Besnagar.	Khambaba pillar, after conservation ...	Full	
4	Udaygiri.	Caves Nos. 5 and 6, general view ...	"	Dupl.
District Gird.				
5	Gwalior.	Hathiapaur gate, general view from west ...	"	
6	"	Khandaura Khan mosque from north west, back view ...	"	
7	"	" " " " distant view from north west ...	"	
8	"	" " " " a mehrab...	Half Full	
9	"	Sarai gateway, general view from north west ...	"	
10	"	A ruined tomb near Khandaura Khan's mosque ...	"	
11	Archl. Museum	Bodhisattva Padmapani (a bronze statue)	Half Full	
12	"	A Tantric figure " "	"	
13	"	A goddess (riding on a lion) " " front view ...	"	
14	"	" " " " " " side view ...	"	
15	"	Siva (?) " "	Half	
16	"	A goddess standing carrying a bell (?) in right hand.	"	
17	"	A horse (a bronze statue)	"	
18	"	A lamp with a figure of Gaja Gauri on back (a bronze statue) ...	"	
19	"	A swing supported on two elephants (a bronze statue) ...	"	Dupl.
20	"	A goddess standing and carrying a lotus bud in left hand (a brass statue) ...	"	
21	"	A duck (a brass statue) ...	"	
22	"	A Bodhisattva seated (a brass statue).	"	
23	"	A goddess standing and carrying a lotus in right hand (a brass statue) ...	"	
24	"	A Drummer riding on elephant (a brass statue) ...	Quarter	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
25	Archl. Museum.	A mouse (?), vehicle of a god (a brass statue).	Quarter.	
26	"	A horseman hunting a tiger with his lance (a brass atatu)	"	
27	"	A bull (Nandi) ... " "	"	
28	"	A Hanumat shaped handle of bell ... " "	"	
29	"	A devotee seated with folded hands ... " "	"	
30	"	Siva slaying Gajasura (a stone sculpture)	Full	Dupl.
31	"	Parvati standing " "	"	
32	"	Kurma <i>avata</i> fragment " "	Half	
33	"	A Jain <i>chaumukha</i> " "	"	
34	"	Kubera ... " "	"	"
35	"	Bhairava standing " "	"	
36	"	A female standing " "	"	
37	"	A goddess in a niche	Quarter	
38	"	Another goddess in a niche ...	"	
District Mandasor.				
39	Sondani.	Yasodharman's pillars, view from south west after conservation ...	Full	
40	"	Yasodharman's pillars, view from north or east after conservation ...	"	
41	"	Two <i>Dvarapalas</i> after conservation ...	"	
42	Chorpura.	An old temple in ruins from south west.	"	
District Narwar.				
43	Narwar Fort.	Fort, a view from south east ..	"	
44	" "	" another view from east ...	"	
45	" "	" " " " south east	"	
46	" "	" " " " " "	"	
47	" "	" " " " " "	"	
48	" "	Makaradhvaj Tal, after repairs, view from north east ...	"	
49	" "	Makaradhvaj Tal, after repairs, view from north west ...	"	
50	" "	Chhip Mahal after clearance ...	"	
51	" "	A stone trough known as Chhip, after repairs ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
52	Narwar Fort.	Ladau Bungalow after repairs ...	Full.	
53	" "	Jamah Masjid after repairs ..	"	
54	" "	" " inscription central panel.	Half	
55	" "	" " " northern "	"	
56	" "	" " " southern "	Half	
57	" "	Dargah Madarshah from north east.	Full	
58	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, after repairs from north east.	"	
59	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, after repairs, interior view showing pillars ...	"	
60	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, interior pillars and ceiling, after repairs ...	"	
61	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, Jali work, after repairs ...	Half	
62	" "	Kachehri Mahal Baradari from south west ...	Full	
63	" "	Kachehri Mahal general view from west ...	"	
64	" "	Kachehri Mahal old gardenplot ...	"	
65	" "	" entrance gate ...	"	
66	" "	" " " ...	Half	
67	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, central panel ...	"	
68	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, northern panel ...	"	
69	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, southern panel ...	"	
70	" "	An old door jamb built in a wall near Havapaur ...	"	
71	" "	Havapaur gate, front view ...	Full	
72	" "	" " side view ...	"	
73	" "	A temple door frame near Havapaur.	"	
74	" "	A Burj after repairs ...	"	
75	" "	Interior of a bastion near Dholapaur.	"	
76	" Town.	Ek-Khamba Chhatri. ...	"	
77	" "	An Armenian tomb near Inspection Bungalow ...	Half	
78	" "	A row of sculptures in the interior of Dehra ...	Full	
79	" "	A sculpture in the interior of Dehra.	"	
80	" "	Jait Khamba after conservation ...	"	Dupl.
81	" "	Sati Sundar Das, after conservation ...	"	
82	" "	Devi on bank of Lakhna Tal ...	Quarter	
District Tawarghar.				
83	Padhavli.	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> before conservation from north west ...	Full	
84	"	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> interior, before conservation, another view ...	"	
85	"	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> , another view ...	"	
86	Rithora.	A group of Sati and Memorial pillars.	"	

APPENDIX No. H.

List of lantern slides made during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality-	Object and description.	Copying negative, if any.	Remarks.
		Pillars.		
1	Besnagar.	Khambaba pillar ...	1	
		Gateways.		
2	Sanchi.	Eastern gate of Stupa No. 1 ...	1	
		Stupas.		
3	"	Stupa No 1, near view ...	1	
4	"	Stupa No. 1, distant view ...	1	
5	Barobodur. (J A V A)	Stupa.		
		Rock-cut Caves.		
6	Udaygiri.	Cave No. 5, Varaha ...	1	Duplicate
7	"	" " 5, and 6, general view ...	1	
8	"	" " 6, Door frame ...	1	
9	"	" " 6, Mahishasuramardini ...	1	
10	"	" " 6, Vishnu ...	1	
11	Bagh.	2. Facade ...	1	
12	"	" " Interior pillars ...	1	"
13	"	" " A Dagoba chamber ...	1	
14	"	" " Buddha with attendants. ...	1	
15	"	" " " " another group ...	1	
16	"	" " 4, Facade ...	1	
17	"	" " Door frame ...	1	
18	"	" " Upper part of above ...	1	
19	"	" " Pilaster ...	1	
20	"	" " Frieze ...	1	
21	"	" " Lion bracket ...	1	
22	"	" " 5 General view, interior ...	1	
23	"	" " 5 and 6 general view ...	1	
		Buddhist Sculptures.		
24	Borobodur. (J A V A)	A scene in Buddha's life ...	1	
25	"	" " " " ...	1	
26	"	" " " " ...	1	
27	"	Buddha ...	1	
		Brahmanic Sculptures.		
28	Gyaraspur.	Siva slaying Gajasura ...	1	
29	Kota.	" " " " ...	1	
30	Badoh.	Yasoda Krishna (?) ...	1	
31	"	" " " " another view ...	1	
32	"	Sri Krishna (?) ...	1	
33	"	Surya ...	1	
34	"	Vishnu ...	1	
		Miscellaneous.		
35	Ujjain.	Observatory, general view ...	1	
36	"	" Samrat Yantra ...	1	
37	Bagh.	Outline of fresco Discourse ...	1	
38	"	" " " 'Music in the air' ...	1	
39	"	" " " Dance ...	1	
40	"	" " " Elephant procession ...	1	
41	"	" " " Wall decoration ...	1	
42	"	Cave No. 2, elevation drawing of Dagoba ...	1	

APPENDIX NO. I.

List of Books added to the Office Library
during the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Archaeological Survey Reports, Memoirs, Etc.		
1	Arch. Surv. of India, Annual Report for 1922-23 ...	Gratis.
2	" " " " " " for 1923-24 ...	"
3	Report of the Superintendent Archaeological Survey of Burma for the year ending 31st March 1926 ...	"
4	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 15. The Drawing of Geometric Patterns in Saracenic Art by E. H. Hankin ...	"
5	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 19. The Jami Masjid at Badaun and other buildings in the United Provinces by J. F. Blakiston ...	"
6	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 20. The Origin and Cult of Tara by H. Shastri ...	"
7	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 21 The Baghela Dynasty of Rewah by H. Shastri ...	"
8	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 22. An Historical Memoir of the Qutb: Delhi by J. A. Page. ...	"
9	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, No. 27. Pageant of Kings of Mindon by Chas-Duroiselle ...	"
10	Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of Ceylon, Vol. II, year 1926 ...	"
Art and Architecture.		
11	Indian Art and Letters Vol. 1, No. 2, November 1925. India Soc. Publication ...	"
12	The Architectural Antiquities of Western India by H. Cousins ...	"
Dictionaries.		
13	Persian English and Urdu Dictionary by S. C. Paul ...	Purchased.
14	" into Urdu Dictionary by Maulvi Karimuddin ...	"
Epigraphy.		
15	The Indo-Summerian Seals deciphered by L. A. Waddell. ...	"
16	Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum Vol. I, inscriptions of Asoka by E. Hultzsch, Ph. D. ...	Gratis,
17-20	Epigraphia Indica Vol. XVIII, Nos. 1 to 4, year 1925 ...	"
21	Annual Report of South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1925 ...	"
Engineering.		
22	P.W.D. Hand Book, Bombay, containing specifications, rates, tables, plates and notes on work Vol. I, by E. L. Marryat. ...	Purchased,
Geography.		
23	Cunningham's Ancient Geography of India edited by S. N. Majumdar ...	"
Guides.		
24	The Seven Pagodas by J. W. Coomber ...	"
25	Guide to Benares by P. Seshadri ...	"
26	" Prayag or Allahabad ...	"
27	" Tanjore by Major H. A. Newell ...	"
28	" Rameswaram by ...	"
29	" Trichinopoly ...	"
30	" Madura ...	"
31	" The collection of the Colombo Museum, Ceylon, Part I. ...	"

No.	Title.	Remarks.
32	Guide to Ajanta frescoes	Purchased.
33	" the Caves of Ellora	"
34	" to the Madras and S. M. Railway (illustrated)	"
History.		
35	Ancient India by Codrington	"
36	" " by Merindle	"
37	History of Caste in India by S. V. Ketkar	"
38	Some Kshatriya Tribes of Ancient India by B. C. Law	"
39-41	History of the Maratha People, Vol. I, II and III, by Kincaid and Parasnis	"
42	History of Mediaeval India, Vol. II, 'Rajputana' by C. V. Vaidya	"
43	Ancient Mid-Indian Kshatriya Tribes, Vol. I, by B.C. Law.	"
44	Hindu Pad Padshahi by V. D. Savarkar	"
45	Dravidian India, Vol. I, by T. R. Sessa Iyengar	"
46	आर्यांचे सणांचा प्राचीन व अर्वाचीन इतिहास, ऋग्वेदी कृत	"
47	मराठी विद्यासत मध्य विभाग ३ गो. स. सरदेसाई कृत	"
Journals and Periodicals.		
48-58	Indian Antiquary for July 1925 to May 1926	"
59-70	Modern Review for July 1925 to June 1926	"
71	Index to Vol. LIV of Indian Antiquary	"
72	The Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XV, No. 4	"
73-76	" " " " XVI, Nos. 1 to 4	"
77-79	The Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol I, Nos. 2 to 4	"
80	" " " " II, No. 1, for March 1926	"
81	The illustrated London News, dated 4th October 1924	"
82	मालव मयूर मासिक, अंक जुलाई १९२५	"
Literature.		
83	Samarangana Sutradhara by King Bhojadeva, Vol. II, edited by Ganapati Shastri	"
84	Notes of a study of the Preliminary Chapters of the Mahabharata by V. V. Iyer	"
85	महाराष्ट्रीय वाङ्मय सूचि (१८१०-१९१७) डा. श्री. व्यं. केतकर कृत	"
86	लेखन कला व लेखन व्यवसाय, वा. गो. आपटे कृत	"
Miscellaneous.		
87	Indian After Dinner, Stories by A. S. P. Iyer	"
88	My Pilgrimages to Ajanta and Bagh by M. C. Dey	"
89	The Arctic Home in the Vedas by B. G. Tilak	"
90	Orion or Antiquity of Vedas by B. G. Tilak	"
91	Hindu Law by S. V. Ketkar	"
92	Things Indian by William Crooke	"
93	South Indian Shrines by P. V. Jagadisa Iyer	"
94	Kautilya Arthashastram edited by R. Sharma Shastri	"
95	" " English Translation by R. Sharma Shastri with an introductory note by the late Dr. J. F. Fleet	"
Numismatics.		
96	Occasional Memoirs of the Numismatic Society of India, II, Historical Studies in Mughal Numismatics by Hodiwala	Purchased.
State Publications.		
97	प्रोसीडिंग्स मजलिस खास मुतमल्लिक होम डिपार्टमेंट, मिन इन्तद्वारा संमत १९६२ उगायत १९८१	Gratis.

APPENDIX No. J.

Statement of income realised during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Heads.	Amount.			Remarks.
		Rs.	a.	p.	
1	By sale of Gwalior Fort Albums ...	175	6	0	
2	„ Tender forms ...	11	0	0	
3	„ Water colour tubes ...	6	4	0	
4	„ photo prints ...	7	8	0	
5	By auction of building material at Udaypur	14	0	0	
	TOTAL ...	214	2	0	

APPENDIX No. K.

Statement of Expenditure incurred during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Heads.	Amount cur-	Amount last	TOTAL
		rent year.	year.	
		Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.
1	Salaries	8,820 13 1	...	8,820 13 1
2	Travelling allowances	2,133 3 0	4 6 0	2,137 9 0
3	Contingencies	1,476 6 3	399 15 0	1,876 5 3
4	Books and Periodicals	381 7 0	6 8 0	387 15 0
5	Museum	1,018 6 0	...	1,018 6 0
6	Works.—			
	(a) Conservation of Monuments ...	3,296 2 9	4,368 2 6	7,664 6 3
	(b) Presenting an album to H. H. the Maharaja Scindia on the auspicious occasion of his coronation	140 1 3	...	140 1 3
	(c) Presenting an album to* Their Mm. the King and Queen of Belgians during Their Mm.'s visit to Gwalior	96 11 0	...	96 11 0
	(d) Publication of a guide to Chanderi.	319 1 9	...	319 1 9
	(e) Exhibiting photographs of Archaeological Monuments in G. I. P. Ry. carriages	400 0 0	...	400 0 0
	(f) Compensation of land acquired at Badoh (District Bhilsa) ...	42 14 0	...	42 14 0
	(g) Departmental At-Home ...	499 9 3	...	499 9 3
	(h) Salaries of work charged staff ...	273 0 0	...	273 0 0
	(i) Sending Bagh frescoes to England.	...	63 5 0	63 5 0
	(j) Publication of Bagh frescoes ...	48 2 0	...	48 2 0
7	Upkeep of conserved monuments ...	333 12 9	82 10 6	416 7 3
8	Sanitation, hot weather and garden charges (over and above budget grant)	163 0 0	...	163 0 0
9	Repairs to buildings on Narwar Fort (Special grant)	...	11,698 0 9	11,698 0 9
	TOTAL Rs. ...	19,442 10 1	16,623 0 9	36,065 10 10

Date	Description	Amount	Balance
1870	Jan 1	100.00	100.00
1870	Feb 1	50.00	50.00
1870	Mar 1	25.00	25.00
1870	Apr 1	15.00	10.00
1870	May 1	10.00	0.00
1870	Jun 1	5.00	5.00
1870	Jul 1	3.00	2.00
1870	Aug 1	2.00	0.00
1870	Sep 1	1.00	1.00
1870	Oct 1	0.50	0.50
1870	Nov 1	0.25	0.25
1870	Dec 1	0.10	0.15
1870	Total	200.00	200.00
1871	Jan 1	0.00	0.00
1871	Feb 1	0.00	0.00
1871	Mar 1	0.00	0.00
1871	Apr 1	0.00	0.00
1871	May 1	0.00	0.00
1871	Total	0.00	0.00

(a) Yasodharman's Pillars at Sondni, before conservation.

(b) Yasodharman's Pillars at Sondni, after conservation.

(b) Siva slaying Gajasura or elephant demon,
from Gyarasput.

(a) Siva at Mandasor, after conservation.

(a) River goddess Yamuna in a panel on the Toran Pillar at Khilchipura.

(b) Toran Pillar (locally known as Sravan ki kavadi) at Khilchipura, after conservation

(c) Another panel of sculpture on the Toran Pillar at Khilchipura.

(b) A decorated arch in the Kacheri Mahal, at Narwar Fort.

(d) Sikandar Lodi's Mosque, at Narwar Fort, after clearance.

(a) The hill Fort at Narwar, general view.

(c) A monolithic trough known as chhip, at Narwar Fort.

(a) A tantric image of Siva ॐ , brass, height 1'4"

(b) A tantric image of a goddess riding a lion ॐ , brass, height 1'8"

(b) Bodhisattva, copper, height 6 $\frac{3}{4}$ "

(a) Bodhisattva Vairapani, copper, height 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ "

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